

**THE VALUE OF INNOVATIVE APPROACHES IN THE
MASSIFICATION OF THE KURASH**

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Abstract

Purpose: The aim of the study is to develop scientifically based proposals and recommendations for increasing the popularity of the national Kurash wrestling.

Methods: The study used pedagogical observations, questionnaires. From among the sports educational institutions, 10 trainers from the children's and youth sports school No. 2 of the city, as well as 10 coaches, took part in the study. During the study, their reactions to the use of scientific achievements were analyzed.

Conclusion: The article deals with the problems of increasing the mass character of the Kurash wrestling, and also develops proposals and recommendations for the further development of work to increase the popularity of Kurash. It also substantiates the need to study the factors influencing the mass character of the Kurash wrestling, and to organize work to introduce innovative approaches to the training of kurash wrestlers.

Keywords: national wrestling, “Kurash”, massification, sports, reserve, sports-rehabilitation stage, training stage, sports skills, education system, science, scientific researches, innovation.

Introduction

Kurash wrestlers of our country win important victories in the world sports arenas. But in order to maintain the achieved high places and further development, it is necessary to continue our work aimed at improving the training process, and efficiency needs to be improved by systematic work on the popularization of the “Kurash” wrestling.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 2, 2017 No. PQ-3306 “On measures to further develop the national sport Kurash” and Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 4, 2020 No. PQ-4881 “On measures to develop and further increase international prestige the national sport of kurash”, as well as other legal documents related to this area, to a certain extent serve to implement the tasks set for the development of the national sport “Kurash”.

As we know, every nation in the world has its own national sport. Since ancient times, there have been peculiar types of wrestling, which are the pride of the Uzbek people. These types include Bukhara style, Fergana style or belt wrestling. Modern Kurash is based on the Bukhara style. The struggle with a centuries-old history that has passed from century to century and has come down to our days, developed over the years and caused joy in the hearts of the fans. Kurash has long been held at various folk festivals and holidays, causing great interest and respect among the people, and therefore Kurash wrestlers were treated as national heroes.

Kurash wrestling is the most popular type of national martial arts in Uzbekistan. Translated from Uzbek, "Kurash" means "achieving the goal in an honest way." This type of wrestling appeared on the territory of modern Uzbekistan about 3.5 thousand years ago and is considered one of the developing sports in the world. On September 6, 1998, at the initiative of the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the International Kurash Association was established, and the national sport, Kurash, received international status.

The continuation of the wide promotion of Kurash wrestling, as well as the inclusion of this sport in the program of the Olympic Games, is a priority. We want as many people as possible to go in for our national sport, to be interested in it in more countries. Today National Kurash Federations operate in 121 states on five continents of the world. Their largest number is registered in Europe and Asia - more than 30 federations.

The aim of the study is to develop scientifically based proposals and recommendations for increasing the popularity of the national Kurash wrestling, and the objective of the study is to determine the state of work carried out in the activities

of sports educational institutions to increase the popularity of Kurash wrestling, as well as to develop the work of coaches to popularize Kurash in sports educational institutions, sports federations.

Methods

The study used pedagogical observations, questionnaires. From among the sports educational institutions, 10 trainers from the children's and youth sports school No. 2 of the city of, as well as 10 coaches from the College of Olympic and Paralympic Reserve, took part in the study. During the study, their reactions to the use of scientific achievements were analyzed.

Results and discussion

Today it is considered necessary to focus on the following issues in ensuring the popularity of the wrestling sport Kurash.

The study of theoretical and practical problems of popularization of the national type of wrestling Kurash among the population;

Development of scientific and organizational bases for the training of qualified specialists, coaches and judges in the national sport Kurash;

Introduction of innovative approaches to the system of training highly qualified kurash wrestlers;

Development of skills and abilities of coaches to use the achievements of modern science in improving the technical and tactical training of highly qualified kurash wrestlers;

Systematic organization of work on the selection of young kurash wrestlers in order to develop a reserve of national teams, as well as a joint fight against attempts to falsify documents and change the age of kurash wrestlers.

The national type of wrestling Kurash has a very ancient history. Although this sport has its own social, philosophical, pedagogical foundations, the ongoing research work to study the development of Kurash does not fully meet modern development requirements.

Currently, Kurash federations operate in more than 130 countries around the world. In a number of countries Kurash is taught as a subject of study in educational

institutions. The fact that wrestling is recognized by the general public in the international sports arena and included in the program of the Asian Games 2018 (Indonesia, Jakarta) contributes to a sharp increase in the number of kurash practitioners in the world.

We conducted a small study in order to analyze the state of work on the massization of the sport of Kurash. Coaches of the children's and youth sports school (children's and youth sports school No. 2 of the city) and coaches of the College of Olympic and Paralympic Reserves () took part in our study.

The study involved 10 coaches from the Children's and Youth Sports School No. 2 and the College of Olympic and Paralympic Reserve, and they were asked questions about the popularization of this sport.

To the question “Do you organize the work to popularize sport among student athletes?”, asked to the coaches of the children's and youth sports school No. 2 of the city of Nukus, 83% of the coaches answered “No, I do not carry out such work”, 17% “Sometimes I do” (Fig. 1)

Figure 2. Diagram of the answers of coaches of the children's and youth sports school No. 2 of the city to the question “Do you organize the work to popularize sport among student athletes?”.

In addition, the question “What kind of innovative style do you use in your work?” was asked, but no one answered it.

When these questions were asked to the coaches of the College of the Olympic and Paralympic reserve of the city, to the question “Do you organize the work to popularize sport among student athletes?” 27% of the coaches answered “No, I do not carry out such work”?, 65% answered “Sometimes I do” and 8% answered “I always do” (Fig. 2)

Figure 2. Diagram of the answers of coaches of the College of the Olympic and Paralympic reserve of the city to the question “Do you organize the work to popularize sport among student athletes?”.

If we analyze the results of the survey, we can see that the level of use of innovative methods for popularizing sports by coaches of the children's and youth sports school No. 2 of the city and the College of the Olympic and Paralympic Reserve of the city is different. The results of this study proved that promotion work in sports schools should be organized from the lower links of the system.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study in general, it should be noted that in this direction it is necessary to find a scientific solution to the following problems:

there are no single and generally accepted terms for Kurash wrestling intended for international and local coaches, judges and experts. This situation, in turn, leads to incorrect or different application and understanding of specific terms specific to Kurash wrestling;

the systematics of Kurash wrestling techniques, their various aspects, as well as the process of their training are not included in a single system. This situation has a negative impact on the process of teaching Kurash techniques of different age and gender groups, specialists in Kurash wrestling in different countries of the world. For this reason, one of the most important conditions for the development of Kurash wrestling is the development of a unified system of Kurash wrestling techniques;

At present, the knowledge, skills and abilities of Kurash wrestling specialists of the republic and foreign countries are evaluated differently. This situation hinders the selection of experienced and qualified Kurash specialists at the international level and in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Therefore, it is important to develop a platform for evaluating the theoretical and practical knowledge, skills and abilities of trainers, referees and experts in Kurash wrestling based on the existing classification of Kurash wrestling techniques;

in modern coaching practice, there is a definition and organization of training and recovery time for kurash wrestling based on various factors. As a result, in most cases, the intervals between exercise and recovery are organized disproportionately, which makes it difficult to achieve the goal set before training. Therefore, it is extremely important for Kurash wrestlers to determine the optimal parameters of training and recovery time based on the analysis of competition results;

Kurash is considered a fast and intense sport. During the competition, various technical actions are performed. In some cases, experts make the right decision, in other cases, disputes arise between them. An extremely important issue is a quick, accurate and efficient assessment of extreme situations during Kurash competitions. For this

reason, it is considered necessary to create a platform of simulated situations, which reflects the different moments that may arise in Kurash wrestling competitions;

there is no mechanism by which foreign or domestic experts in Kurash wrestling could receive information, theoretical and methodological knowledge related to wrestling. Currently, Kurash wrestling specialists receive information from various sources. This circumstance, in turn, indicates the need to develop an electronic platform of the mechanism, which is able to provide theoretical and methodological knowledge to Kurash wrestling specialists.

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